

Corporate Universities and Career Success: A Dyadic Exploration between Training and Perceived Reality.

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Abstract:

This article examines the contribution of corporate universities to employees' perceived career success through a comprehensive literature review and empirical research employing a dyadic framework based on the One-With-Many model. It uses a dual analytic approach: intra-dyadic analysis combining the Framework Method and refined semantic analysis to explore subjective meanings within each dyad, and inter-dyadic analysis to uncover relational mechanisms and emergent collective dynamics. The originality of this research lies in its detailed use of a dyadic "One-With-Many" approach, capturing both individual and collective interactions to reveal how corporate university strategies shape employees' career success perceptions.

Keywords: Corporate Universities, Career success, training, Perceived Reality, Dyadic approach.

Introduction:

In a context marked by profound socio-economic transformations and an unprecedented acceleration of technological innovations, renewed managerial models closely aligned with the strategic demands of contemporary institutional environments are progressively replacing traditional organizational paradigms. This transformation is part of a broader dynamic aimed at promoting organizational agility and sustainable competitiveness by placing continuous learning and the development of adaptable human capital at the core of managerial priorities (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995; Senge, 1990).

From this perspective, corporate universities emerge as structuring mechanisms dedicated to internal training and skills enhancement, contributing simultaneously to the consolidation of organizational identity and the strengthening of companies' strategic positioning (Garavan et al., 2016). Although originally a concept developed in the United States, its implementation in Morocco remains relatively recent and scientifically underexplored, despite the emergence of initiatives such as Barid Al Maghrib University and the Royal Air Maroc e-campus (Chantor & Bennani, 2023).

In light of these observations, this study aims to examine, through a comprehensive literature review and empirical investigations, the contribution of corporate universities to employees' perceived career success, addressing the central question: how do these universities influence professional trajectories within a transforming organizational context?

This article thus highlights the phenomenon of corporate universities and their role in supporting career success as perceived by employees. It then presents the research methodology employed and the results obtained, before concluding with a discussion that emphasizes the key findings.

1. Literature Review and Research Gap

1.1. Corporate Universities: A Brief Overview

Corporate universities, or Corporate Universities, originated in the early 20th century in the United States, where General Motors established the first milestone by acquiring a specialized school in 1919 dedicated to training its own employees.

During the 1950s, General Electric created its own corporate university, marking a turning point in structuring these internal educational systems. This development accelerated in the 1980s, a period during which giants such as Motorola, Disney, and McDonald's designed their own training structures with the aim of homogenizing skills and corporate culture at an international scale. This movement emerged within the industrial society, stemming from the observations of leaders of early American organizations regarding the inability of the educational system to

produce profiles adapted to the developmental needs of their enterprises (Eurich et al., 1985). Despite reforms undertaken to align educational structures with these needs, employee competencies continued to be deemed insufficient. In response, companies such as those aforementioned implemented more targeted and specific training and development programs (Wiggenhorn, 1990, cited by Chantor.B & Houmid Bennani.A, 2023).

Several denominations have been used to refer to the concept of corporate university, including academy, campus, or institute, among others. Eurich et al. (1985) and Meister (1998) contributed significantly to formalizing the understanding of this phenomenon. Meister (1998) describes a corporate university as “a centralized internal training and education center designed to respond to the reduction in the duration of knowledge retention and to promote organizational alignment.” Similarly, Matin Plompen (2005) defines a corporate university as “an organizational space dedicated to the alignment and coordination of all training activities in order to achieve the organization’s objectives.” Likewise, Allen (2002, p. 9) considers the corporate university as “an educational entity, a strategic tool designed to support the parent organization in fulfilling its mission by conducting activities that foster learning, knowledge sharing, and the development of wisdom.”

Thanks to globalization and business growth, the phenomenon of corporate universities truly flourished in the 1970s and 1980s. It was only from the 2000s onward, with the advent of digitalization and the rise of e-learning, that the corporate university model transformed, reaching a broader audience and diversifying its pedagogical modalities and tools.

In Morocco, this movement emerged later, notably in the 2000s, with the establishment of emblematic institutions such as Barid Al Maghrib University, the Royal Air Maroc e-campus, Mamda Digital Academy, Tourism Academy, Ministry of Agriculture Academy, and Tanger Med E-Learning, among others. These entities were primarily founded to implement training and support programs tailored to the intrinsic and extrinsic characteristics of employees

The objectives of these institutes are not limited solely to technical skills enhancement. They also aim to retain employees for as long as possible by cultivating resilient relationships and creating career opportunities alongside more incentivizing motivation mechanisms.

1.2. Corporate Universities and Career success: Exploring Their Interrelationship.

The fundamental rationale behind the establishment of corporate universities lies in their capacity to keep pace with the evolving organizational demands while simultaneously addressing individual developmental needs by offering targeted training programs. These institutions provide employees with the necessary tools and resources to seize career opportunities aligned with their aspirations. Thus, corporate universities function as integrative

mechanisms that bridge learning initiatives with both organizational goals and individual career objectives (Dealtry & Rademakers, 2005), thereby contributing to overall organizational performance (Shaw, 2005).

Contemporary theoretical frameworks conceptualize the nexus between learning and career progression as a dynamic, interactive, and ongoing process. Within these process, acquiring and mastering new competencies is essential for individuals to adapt, advance, and transform in a perpetually evolving professional environment.

Modern learning theories — emphasizing active knowledge construction, the pivotal role of social support (Zone of Proximal Development, ZPD), networked learning or connectivism (Duplâa & Talaat, 2011; Siemens, 2005), learner autonomy, and situated learning (Kolb, 1984) — find tangible and pragmatic application within the corporate university paradigm.

Empirically, corporate universities design their curricula in close alignment with business requirements and market demands, collaboratively co-constructing customized training pathways with operational units. This fosters an active, contextualized, and collaborative learning model, underpinned by the support of trainers and mentors. Such an approach resonates strongly with Vygotsky's (1978) ZPD concept, which underscores the indispensable role of social scaffolding in individual development (Perrenoud, 2004; Brossard, 2004).

Furthermore, corporate universities serve as strategic levers for professional development by offering personalized training and coaching interventions alongside collaborative platforms that embody the connectivist model, wherein learning emerges from continuous networks of interaction and access to diverse resources (Siemens, 2005). These institutions promote employee autonomy in career path management, thereby enhancing self-regulation and individual engagement in professional advancement (Zimmerman, 2002). They also emphasize workplace learning through innovative pedagogical modalities such as e-learning, collaborative platforms, simulations, and project-based activities, facilitating direct skill transfer to authentic work contexts (Schön, 1983; Eraut, 2004).

Additionally, corporate universities actively promote upward mobility (Turner, 1960) and career success by crafting coherent professional trajectories that accentuate opportunities for career progression. The marketing dimension of corporate universities further shapes employees' perceptions of training relevance and engagement, with programs often tailored to their actual needs and delivered in partnership with reputable institutions. The prestigious aura associated with corporate universities incentivizes employee participation and commitment to learning (Chantor & Houmid Bennani, 2025).

To sustain career development, corporate universities are distinguished by their capacity to integrate advanced technologies that enhance learning efficacy and cultivate a digital culture — a core institutional objective achieved through digitalized programs accessible via in-person, remote, or hybrid modalities. The deployment of artificial intelligence within training ecosystems has notably transformed learners' experiences, increasing program attractiveness and personalization through innovations such as adaptive learning, Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), Corporate Online Open Courses (COOCs), immersive simulations and virtual reality (e.g., PITCHBOY), educational chatbots, automated coaching, microlearning modules, and interactive exchange spaces (e.g., “Fun with Methods”). This technology-driven approach enables individualized learning pathways tailored to specific learner needs.

Moreover, corporate universities increasingly adopt agile and collaborative management methodologies, such as PM² (Project Management Methodology), to guide their educational initiatives. By leveraging techniques including brainstorming, design thinking, and creative problem solving, they stimulate collective ideation, generating innovative solutions responsive to emerging competency requirements.

In summary, corporate universities constitute a mutually beneficial model: they empower organizations investing in human capital and provide individuals with a solid platform to accelerate career development. Consequently, they have established themselves as strategic tools for talent management and drivers of sustainable organizational performance.

2. Methodology of Research and Discussion of the Results:

Our research adopts an interpretivist approach, seeking to understand how individuals construct the meaning they attribute to social reality. We focus specifically on lived experiences and the meanings people assign to social phenomena, with particular attention to the phenomenon of corporate universities.

Given the exploratory and qualitative nature of our study, an abductive reasoning approach was adopted. This iterative methodology enabled detailed and ongoing observation of empirical phenomena, while progressively integrating theoretical frameworks to predict relationships among objectives and test them empirically.

To thoroughly investigate the phenomenon of corporate universities and delineate its contours within a specific real-world context, we employed a single-case study design focused on Webhelp University, the internal training structure of Webhelp Morocco, which became Concentrix following the 2024 merger. This monographic approach allowed for an in-depth analysis of a representative and contextually relevant case regarding our research problem.

We implemented a dyadic "one-with-many" interactional design comprising three dyads. Each dyad consisted of one regional training manager and four customer advisors, facilitating the examination of multiple dyadic relationships between one individual and several others (Kenny et al., 2006; Kenny & Winquist, 2001). This design, widely recognized for its ecological validity (Marcus, 2014), is grounded in the principle of reciprocity and provides nuanced insights into relational processes (Kenny et al., 2020).

The selection of customer advisors was based on their role, availability, and frequency of training received, aligned with the objectives assigned to them. Regional training managers were selected based on professional status, geographical distribution, and dyadic similarity. The sample size—15 semi-structured interviews—was determined by theoretical saturation, ceasing data collection when no new significant information emerged.

In line with this approach, two distinct interview guides were employed for customer advisors and regional training managers, respectively. Dyad members were interviewed opportunistically through professional contacts, personal acquaintances, and LinkedIn profiles, adhering to the specifications of the adopted dyadic design (see Figure n°1).

Figure n°1: The Dyadic Model Employed (One-With-Many Design).

Source: Authors.

Interviews with regional training managers were thematically structured, building upon the questions previously posed to customer advisors. These interviews addressed the training policies, support and coaching mechanisms, promotion practices, as well as career management within Webhelp University.

The interview process began with inquiries into Webhelp University’s training policy before shifting focus to the company’s career management strategies, aiming to gauge the extent of Webhelp University’s involvement and contribution to the professional success of customer advisors.

Two complementary types of analyses were conducted. First, an intra-dyadic analysis was performed using Collaço’s (2021) Framework method (see Figure 2), facilitated by the MaxQDA software. This analysis identified three major themes: training strategies, career

management, and contribution to career success. Second, the results were reinforced through semantic similarity analysis employing the Jaccard coefficient, supported by research methodologies utilizing Wordstat and Tropes software, thereby enhancing the robustness and validity of the findings.

Subsequently, a comparative inter-dyadic analysis was carried out to reveal convergences and divergences across dyadic groups, providing a comprehensive understanding of the studied phenomenon.

This rigorous methodology, grounded in abductive reasoning, case study design, and dyadic interactional design, ensures a thorough and context-sensitive exploration of the learning dynamics and career development processes within a corporate university setting (see Figure n°2).

Figure n°2: Adaptation of the Dyadic Analysis Process Using the Framework Method.

Source: Collaço, N., & al (2021).

3. Results:

Presented below are the tables delineating the intra-dyadic analyses conducted for each individual dyad. These are subsequently complemented by a detailed semantic similarity analysis tailored specifically to each dyad. This comprehensive analytical approach facilitates

a nuanced understanding of the relational dynamics within each dyadic pairing and highlights thematic consistencies and divergences across the different units of analysis (see table n°1).

3.1. Intra-Dyadic Analysis of the First Dyad

Table n°1: Analytical Summary of the First Dyad.

Theme	Analytical Summary
Training Strategies of the Corporate University	Members of the dyad acknowledge consistency in the training programs offered since recruitment, tailored to project and employee needs (positions, career paths, seniority). Coaching and support are unanimously deemed essential for project management. However, discrepancies arise regarding the diversity and availability of pedagogical tools: the manager cites a wide range including gamification, e-learning, and virtual reality, whereas some advisors report scarcity of such devices. Overall, training aims at developing the necessary professional skills but does not guarantee immediate promotion.
Observation	Training is closely linked to the company's projects, providing necessary tools for performance, but remains focused primarily on organizational needs.
Career Management Strategies	Advisors mainly perceive interviews, quizzes, and tests as career management tools, while the manager refers to a broader system including pedagogical assessments and annual evaluations. Some advisors express dissatisfaction, criticizing the system as unresponsive and heavily dependent on hierarchical decisions and success in assessment center tests. Webhelp University plays a supportive role in preparing candidates for these tests.
Observation	Webhelp University's contribution to career management is perceived as limited, with the company's strategies appearing poorly adapted to advisors' expectations.
Contribution of the Corporate University to Perceived Career Success	A clear divergence exists between the manager, who values Webhelp University as a lever for professional development and support, and the advisors, whose opinions are mixed. Some express dissatisfaction due to insufficient consideration of their personal aspirations, while others report satisfaction, emphasizing the positive impact of training on their skills and career opportunities.
Observation	Webhelp University meets competency needs related to projects but insufficiently addresses individual employees' aspirations.

Source: Authors.

3.1.1. Semantic similarity analysis (using the Jaccard coefficient) of the first dyad (see figure n° 3)

Figure n°3: Comparison between variables associating Webhelp and Webhelp University.

Source : WordStat

2. Table n°2 :Coefficient Jaccard des variables associant l’UW et Webhelp

	Training	Skills	Knowledge	Coaching	Support	Developpement	Évaluation	Career	Advancement	Promotion	Project	Success
Webhelp	0,112	0,097	0,000	0,011	0,040	0,051	0,071	<u>0,325</u>	0,109	0,083	0,067	0,022
WU	<u>0,351</u>	0,128	0,054	0,027	0,118	0,036	0,061	0,146	0,024	0,000	0,107	0,055

Source: Wordstate

The curves representing Webhelp University and Webhelp contrast the concentration and association of customer advisors’ statements regarding training, skills, knowledge, coaching, support, evaluation, career, advancement, promotion, project, and success. The figure shown below highlights the semantic field of the term “success,” which is influenced by the nouns “project” and “skill” and is more strongly associated with work at Webhelp than with Webhelp University.

Concerning the evolution of their careers, the figure further illustrates that the word “change,” considered a semantic equivalent of “evolution” according to Tropes’ semantic equivalence dictionary, is solely and subtly associated with “work” rather than with “training.” (See figure n°4).

Figure n°4: Presentation of the Semantic Field of the Words "Change, Training, and Work".

Source: Tropes

Extract from Statements

"Training contributes little to the success** of our career. It depends on the project, current events, and the advancement of the customer advisor [...] Support is a key element here; generally, training concerns only the product through which..."**

"My professional success is perfect; otherwise, I would not keep Webhelp as a call center; otherwise, I would change it."

"Professional success is learning; personally, I have acquired new skills, and in terms of salary, it is good, praise be to God."

"For me, career success is based on knowledge and skills. Salary is negotiable."

"We have some internal advancement. (silence) More or less, because it is different; we have several projects, different objectives... Those are their expectations, not ours."

"There are advancement opportunities, perhaps for the more senior employees who want to keep Webhelp as a position or as a job."

"I felt significant advancement after a short period, thanks to these training sessions."

"Then they start to change positions according to the needs of the clients we work with."

"I think Webhelp's strategies will positively influence the advancement of my career given their reputation."

"But it all depends on the advancement of my studies. Among the reasons that pushed me to continue my studies are the working hours at Webhelp and the fact that it (Webhelp or hierarchy)..."

"To change my days off. For me, career success depends on knowledge and skills."

Output: Tropes.

3.2. Intra-Dyadic Analysis of the Second Dyad (see table n° 3):

Table n° 3: Analytical Summary of the Second Dyad.

Theme	Analytical Summary
Corporate University Training Strategies	Customer advisors perceive the training system at Webhelp University as unresponsive, characterized by infrequent sessions primarily deployed reactively to address specific project-related needs. Conversely, the training manager highlights a diverse portfolio of programs and tools designed to develop competencies, foster learning, and strengthen organizational belonging, while ensuring work quality and offering career advancement opportunities. Coaching and support from hierarchical supervisors are central to this strategy. However, a notable discrepancy exists: innovative and certification-based trainings touted by the manager (such as gamification and virtual reality) are regarded by some advisors as conventional and limited, often delivered via digital platforms. Overall, these trainings primarily target operational and commercial demands without broader thematic enrichment.
Observation	Webhelp University aligns its training offerings with commercial imperatives, focusing chiefly on developing the competencies essential for performance.
Career Management Strategies	Webhelp employs a range of tools—including pedagogical assessments, individual interviews, and annual evaluations—to support advisors' professional progression, in collaboration with Webhelp University. Despite these mechanisms, advisors express dissatisfaction, describing the system as complex, ambiguous, and poorly matched to their career expectations, particularly concerning professional advancement.
Observation	The career management policy is perceived as ineffective and insufficiently responsive to the needs of customer advisors.
Perceived Contribution of the Corporate University to Career Success	Despite the presence of training and support structures, advisors consider these strategies inadequate and misaligned with their professional aspirations. While some acknowledge partial benefits, others explicitly voice dissatisfaction, with some contemplating departure from Webhelp.
Observation	Webhelp University's strategies do not sufficiently support the professional success of customer advisors.

Source: Authors

3.2.1 Semantic similarity analysis (using the Jaccard coefficient) of the second dyad.

Figure n°5: Comparison of factors associating Webhelp and Webhelp University in the second dyad.

Source : WordStat

3. Table n°4 : Indice de Jaccard des principales facteurs associant UW et Webhelp.

	Career	Promotion	Evolution	Success	Training	Knowledge	Competencies	Evaluation	Coaching	Support	Development
WU	0,221	0,00	0,04	0,07	0,435	0,13	0,27	0,05	0,02	0,13	0,10
		0	4	9		2	3	3	7	2	0
Webhel	0,508	0,11	0,15	0,02	0,241	0,04	0,12	0,09	0,02	0,04	0,11
p		6	2	2		3	7	5	3	3	1

Source: WordStat

In addition to the table highlighting the main factors influencing customer advisors' perceptions of their career success, the figure and the accompanying table show that customer advisors associate career management practices more strongly with Webhelp, exhibiting a coefficient of 0.508, compared to Webhelp University, which shows a coefficient of 0.435 (see Figure 4 and Table 4).

Semantically, the figure below corroborates the aforementioned results and demonstrates that the term “training” is weakly associated with the career advancement of customer advisors. In other words, the relationship between the item “training” and the words “change” and “career” is infrequent (indicated by a dashed line). Conversely, “training” is rather associated with the terms “skills” and “project.” (See figure n°6)

4. Figure n°6 : Weight of the word “Training” on the Career of Customer Advisors

Output: Tropes.

Extract from Statements

"You know how many people here are waiting for advancement? Many, quite a few people are waiting to progress here."

"Not many, Webhelp has changed. Previously, there were good things, professionalism, lots of training."

"Sometimes there were workshops to change the atmosphere and everything. Unfortunately, currently they do nothing—not activities, not workshops, nothing at all."

"Changing the site and looking for another job. As points to add: Honestly, Webhelp needs more improvement."

"I found myself here, no advancement, especially with the closure of Webhelp's sites since the pandemic."

"Career advancement right now—I don't understand what criteria are taken into account to promote a person, personally."

"That is to say, an opportunity for promotion—Webhelp announces the need and interested parties can apply."

"I can assure you that advancement is difficult, there are many constraints, whether personal or professional. I have been offered promotions many times."

"Career advancement exists at Webhelp but is laborious; several criteria come into play in order for you to apply."

"To progress in my career, whether at Webhelp or elsewhere. Of course, since I work on a banking project by default."

"...career-wise, training programs contribute more or less to my career success, but never 100%."

"We don't have frequent training."

"...frequent means monthly or weekly; the only training we get is during onboarding at Webhelp..."

"Career? Collaborators (silence? normal... sighing; it's not easy to advance)."

"Not necessarily; it has not influenced my career. Yes, of course, they are always attentive to our expectations."

"I started my career at Webhelp in 2011 entirely temporarily, due to lack of job availability."

"There are many criteria that have nothing to do with the nature of the position to be filled or career advancement, and which do not add value to your career, nothing."

"No, I have not succeeded in my career."

"Indeed, we do training at Webhelp whenever there is a novelty or a project need."

"Career advancement exists at Webhelp but is laborious; many criteria come into play for you to apply."

"I feel no effort from Webhelp to manage our careers, no attractiveness; perceived needs are automatically met by other people, personally."

"I don't have a career for it to be impacted (laughs). Well, as I said earlier, training only contributes to ensuring the expected quality of production."

"I am dissatisfied with my career; my work just meets my needs."

"No, it is far from being a success."

Output: Tropes

4. Intra-Dyadic Analysis of the Third Dyad.

5: Analytical Summary of the 3rd Dyad.

Theme	Analytical Summary
Corporate University Training Strategies	Webhelp University offers training programs tailored to the needs of customer advisors, considering project status, seniority, and individual positions. Support and coaching from hierarchical supervisors are essential to ensure effective follow-up and to develop the skills required to achieve the company’s objectives. Although the training modalities are diverse (in-person, remote, virtual reality, gamification), advisors predominantly perceive them as conventional, with a strong emphasis on classroom-based sessions. The curricula primarily focus on technical and interpersonal skills crucial for project management, yet advisors lament the absence of training that facilitates their professional advancement.
Observation	Webhelp University serves as a lever to develop technical and interpersonal skills, contributing to commercial performance and internal career progression, but it does not fully satisfy individual development needs.
Career Management Strategies	Customer advisors report a lack of communication and transparency regarding career management. Despite the use of various evaluation and monitoring tools by managers (interviews, tests, meetings), these mechanisms are deemed insufficient to enable advisors to realize their professional ambitions. The responsible manager asserts that career management is active from onboarding, involving computerized monitoring and support measures; however, this perspective contrasts with advisors’ perceptions, most of whom do not express intentions to progress within Webhelp.
Observation	A career management policy exists but remains vague and only partially aligned with customer advisors’ expectations.
Perceived Contribution of the Corporate University to Career Success	Despite the availability of training and coaching, advisors perceive these strategies as inadequate for addressing their personal and professional needs. Some express significant dissatisfaction and consider leaving the company, whereas others acknowledge a limited influence of these provisions on their career trajectories.
Observation	The impact of Webhelp University on the professional success of advisors remains limited, underscoring the gap between the provisions offered and individual expectations.

Source: Authors

4.1.Semantic similarity analysis (using the Jaccard coefficient) of the 3rd dyad.

Similarly to the previous dyads, we will analyze the semantic similarity within the interviewees' discourse to understand the areas of intervention of Webhelp University in relation to Webhelp’s HR policies. By employing the Jaccard index, several observations were identified.

Figure n°7 illustrates the domains of intervention of both Webhelp University and the Webhelp company.

Figure 7: Comparison between variables associating UW and Webhelp

Source: WordStat

Table n°6: Jaccard Index of the main factors associating Webhelp University and Webhelp in the 3rd dyad.

	Training	Knowledge	Evaluation	Development	Support	Career	Progression	Promotion	Aspirations	Success
Webhelp	0,191	0,175	0,103	0,171	0,119	0,352	0,146	0,051	0,105	0,132
WU	0,389	0,139	0,057	0,050	0,281	0,218	0,051	0,029	0,059	0,121

Source: WordStat

Based on the Jaccard index, it can be observed that the strategies of Webhelp University are more oriented towards the implementation of training and support programs than towards career management, with an index of 0.281.

After highlighting the degree of similarity and association among the variables, the figure below illustrates the semantic field of the term "Training" within the discourse of customer advisors. It is evident that this term is more strongly associated with projects than with career and needs, and it is weakly associated with "development" (denoted by a dashed line).

Figure n°8: Weight of the term "Training" on the career of customer advisors.

Output: Tropes

Extract from Statements

"We undergo training to progress in our careers..."

"In fact, these trainings address production-related needs."

"(Silence) I have no knowledge about Webhelp's career policy; generally, we hold meetings with our managers."

"I do not consider that I will build a career at Webhelp. Low impact. Listen, ma'am, training here is only provided to ensure production quality."

"I am not here to pursue a career. I work for personal reasons."

"As I told you, I am not here to start a new career."

"(Lost) I do not have enough understanding of Webhelp's career management policy."

"Webhelp's trainings influence my career path, especially regarding the project I am involved with..."

"I have just started my career; surely many doors will open, you see..."

"I don't really know how Webhelp manages my career."

"For me, this does not represent career success; my aspirations are quite limited (laughing). Sometimes fate forces you to follow a path..."

"Given the career advancement conditions at Webhelp, Webhelp University will not be able to assist me..."

"(Smiling) The career I wish to pursue does not align with Webhelp's field of activity..."

Output: Tropes

5. Inter-dyad data analysis :

This analysis primarily focuses on comparing the characteristics of dyad members in terms of marital status, age, and gender, as well as their professional experience and previous positions. It also examines their perceptions of Webhelp University's initiatives, their representations of career success, and their views on the contribution of Webhelp University's practices to their career achievement.

Additionally, a comprehensive comparison was conducted regarding the perceptions of the three regional training managers on Webhelp University's contribution to the career success of customer advisors.

Based on the drawn conclusions and after aggregating and synthesizing the testimonies of customer advisors and regional training managers, the following observations were made:

- ✓ One out of twelve customer advisors expressed satisfaction with their job but is seeking new opportunities due to the lack of support from Webhelp University (T2 of the 1st dyad).
- ✓ Eight out of twelve customer advisors expressed dissatisfaction with their career trajectories and the influence of Webhelp University's practices on their career success, including one who declared an intention to leave (T2 of the second dyad).
- ✓ Three out of twelve customer advisors are satisfied with their career paths and Webhelp University's practices, with one also expressing an intention to leave (T2 of the 3rd dyad).
- ✓ Despite Webhelp University's deployment of training and support programs and its involvement in recruitment, onboarding, training, and promotion processes, eight out of twelve customer advisors reported dissatisfaction with these practices. This dissatisfaction primarily stems from the absence of tailored training programs that only address Webhelp's commercial needs and support measures insufficient to sustain their professional development.
- ✓ It is also noted that the nature of Webhelp's commercial projects influences both the frequency and type of training provided.

Overall, twelve customer advisors perceive that Webhelp University's strategies do not contribute to their career success—representing 60% of the interviewed advisors—due to the

lack of personalized training programs, motivation, a healthy social climate, managerial support, and strategic career planning.

6. Discussion and conclusion:

After presenting the results, the table below summarizes the degree of acceptance of the research propositions related to our study:

Table n°7: Level of acceptance of the propositions in our research

N°	Research Propositions	Degree of Acceptance		
		High	Medium	Low
P1	Corporate Universities primarily provide training aimed at strengthening individual competencies and achieving the company's commercial objectives.	X		
P2	Due to the lack of personalized and diverse training and support programs, employee careers are far from being perceived as successful.	X		
P3	The functional model of Corporate Universities proposes strategies aimed at reinforcing employee skills and performance, including career development; however, these practices only marginally influence employees' career success.	X		
P4	Although companies have begun to abandon the application of career development strategies, Corporate Universities continue to manage employees' professional paths through various Human Resource management tools.	X		
P5	Managerial support is one of the key practices of Corporate Universities that strengthen individual competencies and support professional aspirations.			X
P6	Employability and career path management are central concerns of Corporate Universities, which provide employees with the necessary means to seize opportunities aligned with their aspirations.			X
P7	Although Corporate Universities invest in training and support strategies, employees' career success is more closely linked to extrinsic factors such as motivation, salary, and social status than to intrinsic factors.		X	

Source: Authors

The first four propositions (P1 to P4) are supported. Indeed, Webhelp Corporate University directs its efforts toward achieving commercial objectives while offering training programs, support, and evaluation tools designed to enhance the skills of customer advisors and promote their employability. These findings corroborate the work of Meister, Allen, and Keily, who

emphasize that Corporate Universities pursue strategic development at both organizational and individual levels.

However, certain limitations are evident. Propositions 5 and 6, which assumed a strong commitment from Corporate Universities regarding managerial support and internal promotion fostering employability, receive weak acceptance. Our results reveal a notable deficit in hierarchical support, a lack of motivation, and insufficient personalized programs despite the presence of support mechanisms. These shortcomings contribute to a mixed perception of career success among customer advisors.

Finally, proposition 7, which postulates that career success is assessed more objectively by employees, is moderately validated. The data indicate that objective criteria such as remuneration, hierarchical status, and promotion opportunities remain predominant in the evaluation of professional success, relegating intrinsic factors to a secondary role.

These results highlight the complexity of professional development dynamics within Corporate Universities. While training and support strategies are well established, their actual impact on the perception of career success largely depends on organizational and social factors, notably managerial support and extrinsic recognition. These elements constitute critical levers that must be strengthened to optimize the effectiveness of Corporate Universities in career development.

7. Perspectives and Recommendations:

Based on the obtained results and our observations, it appears that Corporate Universities are required to continuously innovate their learning strategies. This involves redesigning learning methods to ensure increased personalization and targeted adaptation to employees' actual needs.

Furthermore, democratizing access to training represents a key factor in guaranteeing engagement and inclusion within the organization. Improving the social climate, combined with the development of smarter and more motivating management mechanisms, remains decisive for ensuring employee performance.

Moreover, for greater precision, Corporate Universities must closely co-manage with company departments to ensure coherence between training strategies, career development, and the organization's overall direction.

Finally, the establishment of competency development pools, along with listening, support, and career guidance mechanisms, proves to be a sine qua non condition for sustainably supporting career pathways and addressing the evolving challenges of the labor market.

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